

PERCEPTION AND SATISFACTION ABOUT THE QUALITY OF ANTENATAL CARE AMONG ANTENATAL WOMEN AT NNAMDI AZIKIWE UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL, NNEWI

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20524355>

Keywords:

Antenatal care, perception, satisfaction, provider attitude, women's experience, Nigeria

Abstract: Background: *Antenatal care quality is shaped not only by access to services but also by women's perception of care providers' attitude, the services received, and the overall care environment. In Nigeria, patient satisfaction with ANC is strongly associated with provider responsiveness, communication, empathy, equipment availability, and ease of obtaining medicines.*

Aim: *This study assessed antenatal women's perception of care providers' attitude and ANC services received, their satisfaction with both, and the factors influencing these outcomes at Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital, Nnewi.*

Methods: *A facility-based descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 170 antenatal clinic attendees at NAUTH, Nnewi. Data were collected using a structured, interviewer-administered questionnaire covering socio-demographic characteristics; perceptions of provider attitude and ANC services; satisfaction with provider attitude and ANC services; and perceived influencing factors. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and presented as frequencies and percentages.*

Results: *Most respondents had a very good or a good perception of both care providers' attitude and ANC services received (59.4%, 56.5%, respectively). Satisfaction was highest for provider explanations (80.2%) and attention (51.0%), but 63.5% were not satisfied with the information received, the waiting time (68.8%), and the facility's neatness (57.3%). Perceived determinants of satisfaction included waiting time (21.9%), staff behaviour (63.5%), space (5.2), and equipment availability (70.8%).*

Conclusion: *Antenatal women at NAUTH generally perceived ANC positively, but dissatisfaction remained in communication, waiting time, and environmental aspects of care. Strengthening provider communication and improving clinic organization are important for better satisfaction*

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Introduction

Antenatal care (ANC) remains a central strategy for improving maternal and perinatal outcomes in low- and middle-income countries, where preventable complications still contribute substantially to mortality (Onyeajam et al., 2018; World Health Organization, 2024). High-quality ANC is not defined solely by coverage or number of visits; women must also perceive the care and the attitude of providers as responsive, respectful, and effective in addressing their needs (Adebowale et al., 2024). Recent Nigerian studies show that women's perception and satisfaction with ANC, particularly with care providers' attitude and the services received, are strongly influenced by waiting time, staff attitude, cost, physical environment, and the availability of essential services and medicines (Adeniji et al., 2021; Adeyemi et al., 2021).

Evidence from different Nigerian settings indicates that many women report high overall satisfaction with ANC but are dissatisfied with specific domains such as long waiting time, overcrowded clinics, poor amenities, and suboptimal communication and interpersonal behaviour from providers (Adeniji et al., 2021; Okonofua et al., 2017; Okonofua et al., 2020). In both primary and tertiary facilities, clients frequently link their perception and satisfaction to care providers' responsiveness, respectful treatment, perceived technical competence, and ease of accessing prescribed investigations and drugs (Onyeajam et al., 2018; Okonofua et al., 2020). These findings suggest that women's views about providers' attitudes and about the content and organization of ANC services are

central to understanding overall satisfaction with care.

Despite efforts to scale up ANC in Nigeria, maternal and perinatal mortality remain high, suggesting persistent gaps in both access and quality of care (Onyeajam et al., 2018; Adebowale et al., 2024). Contemporary studies have shown that women often experience long waiting times, cost barriers, inadequate infrastructure, and unsatisfactory provider-client communication during ANC visits, which can discourage early booking, consistent attendance, and facility-based delivery (Adeniji et al., 2021; Okonofua et al., 2017; Okonofua et al., 2020). In many settings, only about half to two-thirds of women report being fully satisfied with ANC services, despite relatively high utilization, highlighting the need to explore not only satisfaction with services generally but also satisfaction specifically with providers' attitudes and behaviour (Adeniji et al., 2021; Adeyemi et al., 2021; Oduyebo et al., 2023).

Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital (NAUTH), Nnewi, is a major tertiary referral and teaching hospital in Anambra State and a critical provider of ANC and delivery services (Okafor et al., 2022). Within NAUTH, recent work has evaluated mothers' satisfaction with overall maternal and child health services and documented above-average satisfaction with antenatal aspects, but has not provided an in-depth, ANC-specific analysis of how women perceive and rate care providers' attitudes separately from the services they receive (Okafor et al., 2022). There is also limited evidence on how antenatal women in NAUTH perceive the

factors that influence both their perception and satisfaction, such as waiting time, costs, clinic environment, and interpersonal interactions within this particular tertiary context (Okafor et al., 2022). This creates a clear gap for an updated, focused study on antenatal women's perception and satisfaction with care providers' attitudes and with ANC services received at NAUTH, Nnewi, using contemporary concepts of person-centred maternity care.

High-quality, person-centred ANC is central to achieving sustained reductions in maternal and perinatal mortality and to meeting current global and national targets for maternal health (World Health Organization, 2016; Adebowale et al., 2024). Recent evidence indicates that satisfaction with ANC, particularly satisfaction with the attitude of care providers and the organization of services, is associated with continued utilization, adherence to recommendations, and preference for facility-based delivery, while dissatisfaction is often linked to avoidable factors such as waiting time, staff attitude, and out-of-pocket costs (Onyeajam et al., 2018; Adeniji et al., 2021; Oduyebo et al., 2023). Understanding how antenatal women in NAUTH currently perceive care providers' attitudes, how they perceive ANC services received, how satisfied they are with both, and which factors they believe influence these perceptions and satisfaction will therefore provide crucial information for targeted quality-improvement interventions.

For a tertiary teaching hospital like NAUTH, a structured, client-based assessment of ANC quality that explicitly differentiates perception and satisfaction with care providers' attitudes

from perception and satisfaction with ANC services can guide service organization, staff deployment, and the training of medical and nursing students in respectful, woman-centred care (Okafor et al., 2022). The findings will also serve as a baseline for monitoring changes over time and for comparing NAUTH with other facilities within and outside Anambra State, contributing to the broader evidence base on ANC quality in Nigeria (Adeniji et al., 2021; Adeyemi et al., 2021). This study is therefore justified as a timely, context-specific contribution aimed at determining antenatal women's perception of and satisfaction with care providers' attitudes, their perception of and satisfaction with ANC services received, and the perceived factors influencing these perceptions and satisfaction in a key referral centre.

Methods

Research design

This study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional design.

Study area

The study was conducted at Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital (NAUTH), Nnewi, Anambra State, Nigeria. NAUTH is a tertiary referral and teaching hospital that provides antenatal, delivery, and other maternal health services to women from Nnewi and surrounding communities.

Study population: The study population comprised pregnant women attending the antenatal clinic at NAUTH during the study period.

Inclusion criteria: Pregnant women registered for ANC at NAUTH.

Women who have attended at least one ANC visit in the hospital.

Women who are willing to participate and give informed consent.

Exclusion criteria

Seriously ill women who may not be able to complete the questionnaire.

Women who are too distressed or unavailable at the time of data collection.

Women attending the clinic for the first time.

Sample size determination

The minimum sample size was determined using the single proportion formula $n = Z^2pq/d^2$ at a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error. Using an expected satisfaction proportion of 90% from a Nigerian ANC satisfaction study, the minimum sample size was 139. After adding 10% for non-response and a further allowance to strengthen precision for publication, the final sample size was set at 170 respondents.

Sampling technique

A systematic random sampling technique was used to recruit eligible women from the ANC clinic register. The sampling interval was derived from the average attendance and the required sample size. The first participant was selected randomly, after which every k^{th} . An eligible woman was recruited until the sample size was reached. This approach was chosen to reduce selection bias and improve representativeness.

Instrument for data collection

Data were collected using a structured interviewer-administered questionnaire developed from the literature and aligned with the study objectives. The questionnaire had five sections: socio-demographic characteristics, perception of care providers' attitude, perception

of ANC services received, satisfaction with care providers' attitude and ANC services, and perceived factors influencing perception and satisfaction. Responses were measured using Likert-type options to capture graded opinions about service quality, provider behaviour, waiting time, cleanliness, privacy, equipment availability, and communication.

Validity and reliability

The instrument was reviewed by experts in maternal and child health nursing, public health, and research methodology to ensure content validity. A pilot test was conducted in a similar facility outside the study site, and internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. A coefficient of 0.70 or above was considered acceptable for the perception and satisfaction domains.

Data collection procedure

Research assistants administered the questionnaire to eligible respondents after their ANC consultation to minimize recall error and ensure participants had direct experience of the visit they were rating. Participation was voluntary, and confidentiality and anonymity were emphasized. Respondents were assured that their answers would not affect their care.

Variables

The dependent variables were perception of providers' attitude, perception of ANC services, satisfaction with providers' attitude, and satisfaction with ANC services. The independent variables included age, education, marital status, parity, gestational age, number of ANC visits, waiting time, cost, cleanliness, staff communication, availability of equipment, privacy, and space.

Data analysis

Data were coded and analyzed using SPSS version 26 and presented in tables of frequencies and percentages. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the characteristics of respondents and their responses to each item.

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics and Research Committee of the Faculty of Health Sciences and Technology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, and permission was secured from the antenatal clinic authority. Oral informed consent was obtained from all participants. The principles of confidentiality, anonymity, voluntary participation, and the right to withdraw at any point were maintained throughout the study.

Ethical considerations

Obtain ethical approval from the NAUTH Ethics and Research Committee and administrative permission from the antenatal clinic. Ensure informed consent, confidentiality, anonymity, and the right to withdraw without penalty. Because the topic concerns client experience and provider attitude, reassure respondents that their responses will not be linked to their names or affect the care they receive.

Results

Regarding the perception of care providers' attitude, 59.4% of the respondents had a very good perception, 37.7% had a good perception, and 2.9% showed a poor perception (Table 1).

Perception of ANC services was also generally favourable, with 56.5% of the respondents showing a good perception, 41.8% had a very

good perception, and 1.7% a poor perception (Table 2).

Satisfaction with care providers' attitude was mixed. While 51.0% of the respondents were satisfied with the attention they received, 63.5% were not satisfied with the information received, 68.8% were not satisfied with the time spent with them by the providers, 57.3% of the respondents were satisfied with the examination procedures, and 80.2% were satisfied with the level of explanations given (Table 3).

In addition, Satisfaction with ANC services was also varied: 68.8% were not satisfied with the waiting time before being attended to, 74.0% were satisfied with the facility space, 57.3% of the respondents were not satisfied with the neatness of the facility, and 53.1% were not satisfied with the gender of the provider (Table 4).

Among the perceived factors influencing perception and satisfaction, 46.9% of the respondents reported negative encounters with healthcare providers during ANC visits. Among those who reported negative encounters, 21.9% identified long waiting time, 5.2% identified facility space, 2.1% identified facility neatness, and 17.7% identified provider gender as the specific problems. Furthermore, 70.8% believed that the availability of necessary equipment and supplies influenced their perception and satisfaction, 63.5% of the respondents believed that provider behaviour and attitude influenced them, and 76.0% felt that physical infrastructure did not significantly influence their perception and satisfaction (Table 5).

Discussion

Perception of providers' attitude and ANC services

The findings that 59.4% were very good, 37.7% good, 2.9% poor for provider attitude; 41.8% very good, 56.5% good, 1.7% poor for ANC services) indicate predominantly positive perceptions of both providers and services. Several facility-based studies in low- and middle-income settings report similar overall favourable ratings of ANC or maternal services while also documenting substantial pockets of dissatisfaction; the overall positive distribution matches prior work (Kebede et al., 2020; Islam et al, 2022). However, this is in contrast to the study by Nyando et al (2023), which stated that the majority of the women used in the study had a poor perception of the quality of service they received in the antenatal clinic.

Systematic reviews, however, stress that reported positive ratings often coexist with notable negative behaviours (verbal abuse, rudeness, neglect) documented in qualitative and mixed-methods studies, suggesting that high-level positive percentages can mask important negative experiences for a minority of women. The small but non-zero “poor” categories (2–3%) align with that caution: even relatively low proportions of poor experiences are important because they can deter future care-seeking and worsen outcomes (Mannava et al., 2015).

Satisfaction with specific elements of care (attention, information, time spent, examinations, explanations)

The results show a mixed pattern: 51.0% satisfied with attention, 63.5% not satisfied with information, 68.8% not satisfied with time spent, 57.3% satisfied with examinations, and 80.2% satisfied with explanations. This mirrors many

studies that find high satisfaction with some technical or privacy-related elements (examination quality, explanations) but low satisfaction with communication and consultation time (Nwaeze et al., 2013; Onyeajam et al., 2018; Hibusu et al., 2024). Antenatal Care satisfaction in Nigeria may be enhanced by improving responsiveness to clients, clinical care quality, ensuring equipment availability, optimizing easy access to medicines, and expanding free ANC services (Idowu, Israel, Akande, 2022).

Communication and counselling (information provision) repeatedly emerge in the literature as weak points affecting women’s satisfaction and perceived quality, matching your finding that a majority were dissatisfied with the information received. Studies link poor information provision to limited provider time, high caseloads, and inadequate provider training in counselling (Birhanu, 2020; Kebede et al., 2020).

Facility-level satisfaction (waiting time, space, neatness, provider gender)

The respondents reported 68.8% not satisfied with the waiting time, 74.0% satisfied with the facility space, 57.3% not satisfied with the neatness, and 53.1% not satisfied with the provider's gender. Other studies in similar settings report waiting time and cleanliness as common complaints and important predictors of overall satisfaction, so the findings of this study are consistent with prior findings: long waiting times lower satisfaction even when structural aspects (space) are acceptable (Drigo et al., 2020; Emelumadu et al, 2019; Fatile et al., 2016). Provider gender as a dissatisfier is documented elsewhere, where cultural preferences or privacy

concerns influence comfort with male/female providers; your >50% dissatisfaction with provider gender suggests gender-sensitive staffing or options may be important locally and is consistent with studies that identify provider gender as a determinant of uptake or comfort (Emelumadu et al, 2019; Nwaeze et al., 2013).

Perceived factors influencing perception and satisfaction (negative encounters, causes, equipment/supplies, provider behavior and infrastructure)

Nearly half (46.9%) reported negative encounters, and the breakdown (waiting time 21.9%, facility space 5.2%, neatness 2.1%, provider gender 17.7%) emphasizes that waiting time and provider gender are leading specific complaints in this study. This echoes broader evidence that provider behaviour and clinic processes (triage, queuing) are frequent drivers of negative experiences (Fatile et al., 2016; Reis-Muleva et al, 2023).

The respondents' view that availability of equipment/supplies (70.8%) and provider behaviour/attitude (63.5%) influence perception and satisfaction is strongly supported in the literature: facility readiness and functional supplies materially affect perceived quality, and providers' interpersonal skills are repeatedly shown to shape satisfaction and future care-seeking (Kebede et al., 2020).

The finding that 76.0% felt physical infrastructure did not significantly influence their perception is notable; it may reflect that some technical or interpersonal aspects (supplies and behaviour) matter more to users than large-scale infrastructure, which is consistent with studies showing that cleanliness, privacy,

communication, and availability of medicines/equipment often weigh more heavily than grand infrastructure in shaping experience (Kebede et al., 2020; Reis-Muleva et al, 2023).

Concordance with prior evidence, overall favourable ratings alongside significant dissatisfaction with communication, waiting time, and interpersonal aspects fit the commonly reported pattern in maternal health research. Women often report general satisfaction but identify specific, actionable deficits in care processes and provider communication (Mannava et al., 2015).

Queue-management, task-shifting (using community health workers or midwives for health education), and appointment systems have been shown to reduce waiting times and improve perceived time with providers (Kebede et al., 2020).

The findings of this study show an apparent paradox (high overall perception but important dissatisfaction). The literature suggests social desirability, low expectations, or comparison with worse alternatives may inflate overall satisfaction scores while more specific items uncover real problems; qualitative studies show that even when women rate services positively overall, they will still report episodes of neglect or poor communication (Nwaeze et al., 2013).

Ensuring reliable availability of basic equipment and supplies is also essential because users of ANC services in this study and elsewhere identify these as major determinants of perceived quality (Reis-Muleva et al, 2023; Mekie et al., 2024).

Communication training and respectful maternity care initiatives reduced reports of verbal abuse and improved patient experience in

multiple settings, according to systematic reviews and program reports (Mannava et al., 2015; Mandiwa & Namondwe, 2024).

Conclusion

The study showed that respondents generally had a favorable perception of care providers' attitude and ANC services, but their satisfaction was mixed across different aspects of care. While attention received, examination procedures, and explanations given were rated positively, dissatisfaction was prominent in the information received, time spent with providers, waiting time, and the neatness of the facility.

The findings also indicate that client experience is shaped not only by interpersonal factors such as provider behaviour and attitude, but also by service factors like the availability of equipment and supplies. Negative encounters during ANC visits, long waiting times, and provider gender preferences were important contributors to dissatisfaction. Overall, the study suggests that improving respectful communication, reducing waiting time, ensuring cleanliness, and maintaining adequate supplies are essential for enhancing women's perception and satisfaction with antenatal care services.

Recommendations

In line with the findings of this study, which are consistent with reviews and empirical studies, researchers recommend that health care facilities should:

Strengthen interpersonal and communication skills through in-service training and supervision to improve information provision and counselling.

Streamline clinic processes (appointment systems, triage, staffing) to reduce waiting times

and increase the time providers spend with clients.

Implement provider communication and respectful-care training, with follow-up supervision and client-feedback loops.

Introduce or improve appointment/triage systems and consider dedicated health education time or cadre to reduce waiting and improve information provision.

Prioritize reliable provision of essential equipment and supplies and routine facility cleanliness audits, since both supplies and neatness influence perceived quality.

Monitor gender preferences in staffing and offer options where feasible to respect patient comfort and cultural norms.

Strengths and limitations

The main strength of the study is that it focuses on a tertiary teaching hospital and separately measures perception and satisfaction with both provider attitude and ANC services. Another strength is that it captures the women's own views, which are essential for client-centred quality improvement. A limitation is that a cross-sectional design cannot establish causality, only associations. Also, satisfaction responses may be influenced by social desirability bias if participants fear their responses could affect care.

Acknowledgements

The researchers appreciate our respondents for their contributions to this study. We are very grateful to the Ethics and Research Committee of the Faculty of Health Sciences and Technology for their approval to carry out this study. We also thank the head of the ANC unit where pregnant women were recruited for their assistance.

Funding

This study was not funded

Ethical approval to conduct the study

Approval to conduct the study was given by the Ethics and Research Committee of the Faculty of Health Sciences and Technology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University.

Consent for publication

Not applicable

Declaration of conflict of interests

The authors declared no potential conflict of interest.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon request.

Fundings

No grant was obtained for this study

Conflict of Interest

None

Table 1: Antenatal women's perception about the attitude of antenatal care providers

n=170

Perception	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very good perception (70 & above) %	101	59.4
Good perception (50 -69) %	64	37.7
Poor perception (below 50%)	5	2.9
Total	170	100.0

Table 2: Antenatal women's perception about the quality of antenatal care received,

n=170

Perception	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very good perception (70% & above)	71	41.8
Good perception (50 -69) %	96	56.5
Poor perception (below 50%)	3	1.7
Total	170	100.0

Table 3: Antenatal women's satisfaction with the attitude of antenatal care providers

n=170

Items	Category	Yes (%)	No (%)
Were you satisfied with the following attitudes of the antenatal care providers?	Attention received	87(51.0)	83(49.0)
	Information exchange	62(36.5)	103(63.5)
	The time that the healthcare provider spent with you	53(31.3)	117(68.8)
	Examination procedures	97(57.3)	73(42.7)
			136(80.2)

Level of explanations

Table 4: Antenatal women's satisfaction with the quality of antenatal care received, n=170

Items	Category	Yes (%)	No (%)
Were you satisfied with the following services during antenatal care?	Time spent waiting to be attended to	53(31.3)	117(68.8)
	Facility space	126(74.0)	44(26.0)
	Facility neatness	73(42.7)	97(57.3)
	Gender provider	80(46.9)	90(53.1)

Table 5: Perceived factors influencing perception and satisfaction n=170

Items	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Have you ever experienced any negative encounters with healthcare providers during your antenatal visits at NAUTH Nnewi?	Yes	80	46.9
	No	90	53.1
	Total	170	100.0
If yes to the question above, please select	Time spent in waiting to be attended to	37	21.9
	Facility space	9	5.2
	Facility neatness	4	2.1
	Gender provider	30	17.7
	Total	170	46.9
Does the availability of necessary equipment and supplies influence your perception and satisfaction with the antenatal care received at NAUTH Nnewi?	Yes	120	70.8
	No	50	29.2
	Total	170	100.0
Does the behavior and attitude of healthcare providers affect your	Yes	108	63.5
	No	62	36.5
	Total	170	100.0

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perception and satisfaction with the antenatal care received at NAUTH Nnewi?

Does the physical infrastructure and quality of the antenatal care facility impact your perception and satisfaction with the antenatal care received at NAUTH Nnewi?	Yes	41	24.0
	No	129	76.0
	Total	170	100.0

Authors' contributions

All authors were involved in the conception of the research idea, design, and implementation of the project. Literature was reviewed by CCHO, CGC, and VCO. Data collection and data entry were done by CGC. VCO wrote the first draft of the manuscript. CCHO critically reviewed the manuscript. CCHO wrote the final manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript and this submission.

Funding

This study was not funded

Ethical approval to conduct the study

Approval to conduct the study was given by the Ethics and Research Committee of Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital, Nnewi.

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Consent for publication

Not applicable

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